

Appendix A: Supplementary maps

- **NGC 3512:** late-type, face-on spiral ($i < 30^\circ$), hosting an AGN. Exhibits a kinematically distinct central depression ("hole") in its cold stellar component, as revealed by dynamical modelling. Some of the emission-line maps show tentative evidence of morphological substructure within the bulge radius, although EW maps display no emission, with exception of [OIII]. No clear bar-like feature is detected in either the photometric or kinematic data. The galaxy forms a physical pair.

Surface Photometry

NGC3512

B/T: 0.27

Fig. A.1. Left panel: K-band photometric image of the NGC 3512, as observed by UHS. The small circle indicates the bulge radius as assessed by the Sérsic fit. Right panel: Derived SBP with a blue line indicating the best-fitting Sérsic model to the central luminosity excess. The vertical dashed line represents the bulge radius as determined by the Sérsic fit. Derived bulge-to-total is displayed above the left panel. The MUSE field-of-view (FoV) fully covers this galaxy.

Spectral Synthesis

Fig. A.2. Subset of spatially resolved stellar population and nebular emission properties of the galaxy, derived with FADO, adopting the Z4 SSP Library. Top row (left to right): present-day and ever-formed stellar mass (M_{now} , M_{ever}), mass- and light-weighted stellar ages ($\langle t_* \rangle_M$, $\langle t_* \rangle_L$), and mass- and light-weighted stellar metallicities ($\langle Z_* \rangle_M$, $\langle Z_* \rangle_L$). Bottom row (left to right): $H\alpha$ flux, $\text{EW}(H\alpha)$, $H\beta$ flux, $\text{EW}(H\beta)$, [O III] $\lambda 5007$ flux, and $\text{EW}([\text{O III}] \lambda 5007)$. White contours trace the K-band morphology, and the circle indicates the bulge radius.

Dynamical modelling

Fig. A.3. Comparison of observed velocity moments (top row), best-fit model moments (middle row), and residuals (bottom row) from the DYNAMITE dynamical modelling for NGC 3512. Overplotted are the K-band contours, as well as a circle defining the bulge radius.

Relationships between the open parameters (p , q , Y_r , M_{200} , and M_*) explored during the dynamical modelling process of NGC 3512, with best-fitting values of $p = 0.99$; $q = 0.21$; $Y_r = 2.63$; $\log(M_{200}) = 3$, $\log(M_*) = 7.1$.

Fig. A.4. Parameter-space exploration for the dynamical modelling of NGC 3512.

Fig. A.5. Panel a) circularity plot showing the distribution of stellar orbits in the best-fit dynamical model of NGC 3512. Horizontal lines denote the separations between cold, warm, hot, and counter-rotating orbits, with default cut values of $\lambda_z < 0.8$; $0.8 > \lambda_z > 0.25$. Panel b) enclosed mass profiles for the stellar (mass-follows-light) component, dark matter, and their sum. Panel c) intrinsic axis ratios q and p as functions of distance from the center; T quantifies triaxiality. Vertical dashed lines indicate the bulge radius.

Orbital Decomposition

Fig. A.6. SBPs of the different dynamical components of NGC 3512, obtained through dynamical modelling and subsequent decomposition. Shaded regions indicate 1σ uncertainties, derived from models whose χ^2 values lie within 1σ of the best-fit solution. Panel a) displays the SBPs of the cold (blue), warm (purple) and hot (red) components, while panel b) displays the SBPs of disk and bulge, where the disk's is obtained by accounting for both cold and warm orbits – displaying a $\eta_e = 3.7$ – while the bulge corresponds to the hot stellar component. The vertical line depicts the bulge radius as obtained through K-band surface photometry.

- **NGC 1285**: face-on, barred spiral, displaying a kinematically distinct central depression in its cold stellar component, as revealed by dynamical modelling. The FADO-derived emission maps show no significant substructure within the bulge region. The galaxy hosts a bar and appears mostly isolated.

Surface Photometry

NGC1285

B/T: 0.17

Fig. A.7. Left panel: K-band photometric image of the NGC 1285, as observed by VHS. Right panel: Derived SBP. Same layout as Fig. A.1. The MUSE FoV fully covers this galaxy.

Spectral Synthesis

Fig. A.8. Subset of FADO results for NGC 1285. Same layout as Fig. A.2.

Dynamical modelling

Fig. A.9. DYNAMITE best-fit models for NGC 1285. Same layout as Fig. A.3.

Relationships between the open parameters (p , q , M_{200} , and Υ_r) explored during the dynamical modelling process of NGC 1285, with best-fitting values of $p = 0.99$; $q = 0.28$; $\Upsilon_r = 2.5$; $\log(M_{200}) = 0.1$, assuming $\log(M_\star) = 7.75$ (Arzoumanian et al. 2021).

Fig. A.10. Parameter-space exploration for the dynamical modelling of NGC 1285.

Fig. A.11. Circularity, enclosed mass and intrinsic axis ratios plots obtained with DYNAMITE. Same layout as Fig. A.5.

Orbital Decomposition

Fig. A.12. Dynamical SBPs of NGC 1285. Same layout as Fig. A.6. The Sérsic fit to the disk has resulted in a $\eta_e = 3.5$.

- **NGC 5248:** flocculent intermediate spiral at $\sim 40^\circ$ inclination. Dynamical modelling suggests that this galaxy hosts a cold stellar component that follows an approximately exponential profile. The stellar kinematic maps reveal a prominent central disk (more extended and not as compact as the nuclear disks identified in other sampled galaxies), likely accounting for the quasi-exponential profile inferred for the cold component from dynamical modelling. Additionally, the central region displays kinematic signatures consistent with spiral structures, evident in the velocity dispersion map (resembling the features seen in NGC 4030, see Breda et al. 2024b), in the stellar age maps, and in the emission line maps. The bump in the photometric SBP, frequently indicative of a bar-like structure, is likely the star-forming disk surrounding the bulge rather than a true bar. The galaxy appears to have 2 relatively close companions, with no significant signs of recent interactions.

Surface Photometry

NGC5248

Fig. A.13. Left panel: K-band photometric image of the NGC 5248, as observed by VHS. Right panel: Derived SBP. Same layout as Fig. A.1. The MUSE FoV fully covers this galaxy.

Spectral Synthesis

Fig. A.14. Subset of FADO results for NGC 5248. Same layout as Fig. A.2.

Dynamical modelling

Fig. A.15. DYNAMITE best-fit models for NGC 5248. Same layout as Fig. A.3.

Relationships between the open parameters (p , q , M_{200} , and Υ_r) explored during the dynamical modelling process of NGC 5248, with best-fitting values of $p = 0.98$; $q = 0.67$; $\Upsilon_r = 1.45$; $\log(M_{200}) = 2$, assuming $\log(M_\bullet) = 6.3$ (van den Bosch 2016).

Fig. A.16. Parameter-space exploration for the dynamical modelling of NGC 5248.

Fig. A.17. Circularity, enclosed mass and intrinsic axis ratios plots obtained with DYNAMITE. Same layout as Fig. A.5.

Orbital Decomposition

Fig. A.18. Dynamical SBPs of NGC 5248. Same layout as Fig. A.6. The Sérsic fit to the disk has resulted in a $\eta_e = 4.7$.

- **IC 2560:** Barred spiral $\sim 60^\circ$ inclination, hosting a kinematically cold nuclear stellar disk, as revealed by dynamical modelling. A X-shaped + bar structure is evident in the photometry (boxy/peanut bulge candidate). Classified as a Seyfert-2 AGN with strong ionized gas emission and resides in a group. Spiral-like features are evident in most emission-line maps.

Surface Photometry

IC2560

B/T: 0.35

Fig. A.19. Left panel: K-band photometric image of the IC 2560, as observed by VHS. Right panel: Derived SBP. Same layout as Fig. A.1. The MUSE FoV fully covers this galaxy.

Spectral Synthesis

Fig. A.20. Subset of FADO results for IC 2560. Same layout as Fig. A.2.

Dynamical modelling

Fig. A.21. DYNAMITE best-fit models for IC 2560. Same layout as Fig. A.3.

Relationships between the open parameters (p , q , M_{200} , and Y_r) explored during the dynamical modelling process of IC 2560, with best-fitting values of $p = 0.90$; $q = 0.39$; $Y_r = 2.35$; $\log(M_{200}) = 1.625$, assuming $\log(M_\bullet) = 7.64$ (van den Bosch 2016).

Fig. A.22. Parameter-space exploration for the dynamical modelling of IC 2560.

Fig. A.23. Circularity, enclosed mass and intrinsic axis ratios plots obtained with DYNAMITE. Same layout as Fig. A.5.

Orbital Decomposition

Fig. A.24. Dynamical SBPs of IC 2560. Same layout as Fig. A.6. Attempts to fit a Sérsic profile to the disk were unsuccessful.

- **NGC7364:** S0/a galaxy hosting a central hole in its kinematically cold component, as inferred from dynamical modelling. Equivalent widths of most emission-line maps also reveal a notable central cavity, reaching their minimum within the bulge region. The galaxy is classified as a LINER and resides in an isolated environment.

Surface Photometry

Fig. A.25. Left panel: K-band photometric image of the NGC 7364, as observed by UKIDSS. Right panel: Derived SBP. Same layout as Fig. A.1. The MUSE FoV fully covers this galaxy.

Spectral Synthesis

Fig. A.26. Subset of FADO results for NGC 7364. Same layout as Fig. A.2.

Dynamical modelling

Fig. A.27. DYNAMITE best-fit models for NGC 7364. Same layout as Fig. A.3.

Relationships between the open parameters (p , q , M_{200} , and Υ_r) explored during the dynamical modelling process of NGC 7364, with best-fitting values of $p = 0.84$; $q = 0.26$; $\Upsilon_r = 3.05$; $\log(M_{200}) = 2.34$, assuming $\log(M_\odot) = 7.61$ (Arzoumanian et al. 2021).

Fig. A.28. Parameter-space exploration for the dynamical modelling of NGC 7364.

Fig. A.29. Circularity, enclosed mass and intrinsic axis ratios plots obtained with DYNAMITE. Same layout as Fig. A.5.

Orbital Decomposition

Fig. A.30. Dynamical SBPs of NGC 7364. Same layout as Fig. A.6. The Sérsic fit to the disk has resulted in a $\eta_e = 1.6$.

- **NGC 0863:** S0/a galaxy at $\sim 45^\circ$ inclination, classified as a Seyfert-2 AGN. It hosts a kinematically cold nuclear disk, as revealed by dynamical modelling, although not as prominent as other galaxies in this sample. High-resolution EW emission-line maps evince very well defined spiral features within the bulge region, surrounded by a pronounced ring, evident in most emission-line flux maps. It has a close companion, though shows no apparent tidal features.

Surface Photometry

NGC0863

B/T: 0.55

Fig. A.31. Left panel: K-band photometric image of the NGC 0863, as observed by UKIDSS. Right panel: Derived SBP. Same layout as Fig. A.1. The MUSE FoV fully covers this galaxy.

Spectral Synthesis

Fig. A.32. Subset of FADO results for NGC 0863. Same layout as Fig. A.2.

Dynamical modelling

Fig. A.33. DYNAMITE best-fit models for NGC 0863. Same layout as Fig. A.3.

Relationships between the open parameters (p , q , M_{200} , and Y_r) explored during the dynamical modelling process of NGC 0863, with best-fitting values of $p = 0.99$; $q = 0.08$; $Y_r = 3.6$; $\log(M_{200}) = 2.87$, assuming $\log(M_*) = 7.68$ (Peterson et al. 2004).

Fig. A.34. Parameter-space exploration for the dynamical modelling of NGC 0863.

Fig. A.35. Circularity, enclosed mass and intrinsic axis ratios plots obtained with DYNAMITE. Same layout as Fig. A.5.

Orbital Decomposition

Fig. A.36. Dynamical SBPs of NGC 0863. Same layout as Fig. A.6. The Sérsic fit to the disk has resulted in a $\eta_e = 3$.

References

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